

Dawn VIR Sequence report for Vesta Science LAMO (VSL) (vir_da022)

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ABSTRACT

This document constitutes the official flight operation report for the VIR (Visible and Infrared Mapping Spectrometer) instrument onboard the Dawn spacecraft, specifically covering the commanding and sequencing activities performed for the vir_da022 session. These operations were executed as part of the VSL phase.

The mission profile focused on the observational sequences for the characterization of the planetary body Vesta, aiming to map its mineralogical features and surface properties.

The report details the generation of the instrument's commanding sequences and the formal verification process. All sequences have been checked against the mission's flight and guideline rules within the SASF (Spacecraft Activity Sequence File) framework. Furthermore, the VIR SASF files were successfully integrated with the sequences of the other onboard instruments to ensure system-level compatibility and resource management. The final integrated sequences were successfully uploaded and executed on the spacecraft during the scheduled vir_da022 window.

KEYWORDS

VIR • Spectral Instrument • Dawn NASA Mission

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References

- [1] M. de Sanctis et al., "The VIR Spectrometer," *ISSR*, vol. 163, no. 1–4, pp. 329–369, Dec. 2011, doi: 10.1007/s11214-010-9668-5.
- [2] A. K. J. Stipanuk, "Spacecraft Activity Sequence File (SASF) Interface.," *Deep Space Mission System (DSMS) Subsystem Software Interface Specification*, 2004.

1. Check list of the sequence vir_vsl_98LAMO.r01.sasf

The following table presents the checklist of the validation tests performed on the vir_vsl_98LAMO.r01.sasf sequence. The OK column indicates successful test execution, while the NA (Not Applicable) column denotes tests that are not relevant to this specific sequence. The P (Pending) column identifies tests that have failed or require further resolution. The Item column serves as a unique identifier for each performed test, and the Description column provides a concise summary of the specific verification criteria.

OK	NA	P	Item	Description
Flight Rules				
✓	□	□	F-VIRC09	VIR cryocooler cool down time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC10	VIR cover actuation time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC11	Allow enough time for VIR to transition to STAND_BY after a SCIENCE mode
□	✓	□	F-VIRC12	Allow enough time for VIR to STAND_BY after issuing VIR_MM_DUMP command
✓	□	□	F-VIRA16	VIR timing requirements for repetition time and integration time
Guideline				
Syntax and grammar analysis				
✓	□	□	G-VIRO1	Syntax and grammar analysis
✓	□	□	G-VIRO2	File name and revision number
✓	□	□	G-VIRO3	The execution of the sequence occurs within the time boundaries (APPLICABLE-(START&STOP)-TIME)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO4	BEGIN and CUTOFF are equal to boundaries
✓	□	□	G-VIRO5	Required of VML_START
✓	□	□	G-VIRO6	if VML_START, file buffer loaded (d:/fb05)
✓	□	□	G-VIRO7	Numerical parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO8	String parameters are in the range
✓	□	□	G-VIRO9	Integration time and delay time are such that the two channels window timing are centered
✓	□	□	G-VIRO10	Do not use epochs_labels different from those defined in EPOCH_DEF
Running and simulating of the sequence				
✓	□	□	G-VIR11	No duplicates found in the list of requests names
✓	□	□	G-VIR12	VIR Mode transition
□	✓	□	G-VIR13	All VIR command have time for execution
✓	□	□	G-VIR14	There are partial dumps
□	□	✓	G-VIR15	No time overlap between the requests
✓	□	□	G-VIR16	Cover open during Science acquisition
□	✓	□	G-VIR17	There are critical commands accepted
□	✓	□	G-VIR18	Cryocooler used only when need
□	✓	□	G-VIR19	When using VIR_SAFE or VIR_TC_MM_CONF is required the Mass Memory to have all pages empty
✓	□	□	G-VIR20	Avoid MM overflow

1.1 List of operations

The following table details the operational operations executed within the vir_vsl_S8LAMO.r01.sasf sequence. For each operation, the start time, stop time, and duration (expressed in seconds) are reported.

Request Name	Start Time[s]	Stop Time[s]	Duration[s]
VIR_VSL_VMLSTART_S8LAMO	385333793	385333795	2
VIR_VSL_C15FullCalibration_001	385333853	385346470	12617
VIR_VSL_C15OpenCover_001	385346753	385346793	40
VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001	385355876	385358228	2352
VIR_VSL_C15DumpDataToVR4_001	385358276	385363077	4801
VIR_VSL_C15PushBroomToVIR_002	385374996	385376384	1388
VIR_VSL_C15DumpDataToVR4_002	385376796	385381597	4801
VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003	385389122	385391474	2352
VIR_VSL_C15DumpDataToVR4_003	385391522	385396323	4801
VIR_VSL_C15PushBroomToVIR_004	385406601	385407989	1388
VIR_VSL_C15CryocoolerOff_001	385408281	385408288	7
VIR_VSL_C15CloseCover_001	385410261	385410299	38
VIR_VSL_C15DumpDataToVR4_004	385410381	385415182	4801
VIR_VSL_C15SAFEmode_001	385415181	385415302	121
VIR_VSL_C16CryocoolerOn_001	385923059	385933860	10801
VIR_VSL_C16OpenCover_001	385933859	385934199	340
VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001	385943011	385945363	2352
VIR_VSL_C16DumpDataToVR4_001	385945411	385950212	4801
VIR_VSL_C16PushBroomToVIR_002	385962223	385963611	1388
VIR_VSL_C16DumpDataToVR4_002	385964023	385968824	4801
VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003	385976445	385978797	2352
VIR_VSL_C16DumpDataToVR4_003	385978845	385983646	4801
VIR_VSL_C16PushBroomToVIR_004	385994043	385995431	1388
VIR_VSL_C16CryocoolerOff_001	385995723	385995730	7
VIR_VSL_C16CloseCover_007	385997643	385997681	38
VIR_VSL_C16DumpDataToVR4_004	385997763	386002564	4801
VIR_VSL_C16SAFEmode_001	386002563	386002684	121
VIR_VSL_VMLEND_S8LAMO	386002743	386002744	1

1.2 Memories usage

Ecco la traduzione in inglese tecnico-scientifico, ottimizzata per la descrizione di grafici di telemetria e occupazione dati:

Technical English Translation The following plots illustrate the data volume and memory occupancy for both the VIR infrared (IR) and visible (VIS) channels. The transitions between the various instrument operational modes are indicated by the green vertical lines.

2. Integrated sequence: da022b.01.filter.rsoe

The following table presents the checklist of the validation tests performed on the da022b.01.filter.rsoe sequence. The OK column indicates successful test execution, while the NA (Not Applicable) column denotes tests that are not relevant to this specific sequence. The P (Pending) column identifies tests that have failed or require further resolution. The Item column serves as a unique identifier for each performed test, and the Description column provides a concise summary of the specific verification criteria.

The VIR instrument was configured to acquire 2 calibration cubes and 80 cubes for IR channel and 80 for VIS channel.

OK	NA	P	Item	Description
Flight Rules				
✓	□	□	F-VIRC09	VIR cryocooler cool down time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC10	VIR cover actuation time
✓	□	□	F-VIRC11	Allow enough time for VIR to transition to STAND_BY after a SCIENCE mode
✓	□	□	F-VIRC12	Allow enough time for VIR to STAND_BY after issuing VIR_MM_DUMP command
✓	□	□	F-VIRA16	VIR timing requirements for repetition time and integration time
Guideline				
Running and simulating of the sequence				
✓	□	□	G-VIR12	VIR Mode transition
✓	□	□	G-VIR13	All VIR command have time for execution
✓	□	□	G-VIR14	There are partial dumps
✓	□	□	G-VIR15	No time overlap between the requests
✓	□	□	G-VIR16	Cover open during Science acquisition
✓	□	□	G-VIR17	There are critical commands accepted
✓	□	□	G-VIR18	Cryocooler used only when need

3. Appendix

This appendix contains the SASF (Spacecraft Activity Sequence File) sequences referenced in this report, along with the SPICE meta-kernel employed for the geometric computations and reference frame transformations.

The following SASF files were processed:

3.1 The sequence: vir_vsl_S8LAMO.r01.sasf

1	CCSD3ZF0000100000001NJPL3KS0L015\$\$MARK\$\$;	sasf
2	MISSION_NAME = DAWN;	
3	SPACECRAFT_NAME = DAWN;	
4	DATA_SET_ID = SPACECRAFT_ACTIVITY_SEQUENCE_DSC;	
5	FILE_NAME = vir_vsl_S8LAMO.r01.sasf;	
6	APPLICABLE_START_TIME = 2012-077T22:55:00.000;	

```
7  APPLICABLE_STOP_TIME = 2012-092T10:00:00.000;
8  PRODUCT_CREATION_TIME = 2012-058T08:49:32.000;
9  PRODUCER_ID = VIRTEAM;
10 SEQ_ID = vir_vsl_S8LAMO.r01;
11 HOST_ID = dawndsc2;
12 CCSD3RE00000$$MARK$$NJPL3IF0M01300000001;
13 $$DWN      SPACECRAFT ACTIVITY SEQUENCE FILE
14 *****
15 *PROJECT    DWN
16 *SPACECRAFT 203
17 *OPERATOR   sfonte
18 *FILE_CMPLT TRUE
19 *DATE       Mon Feb 27 08:49:32 2012
20 *SEQGEN     V29.5.2 Thu Nov 29 13:34:23 PST 2007
21 *BEGIN      2012-077T22:55:00.000
22 *CUTOFF     2012-092T10:00:00.000
23 *TITLE      VIR_VSL_da022_Sequence_8
24 *EPOCHS_DEF
25 *SEQ_VSL_C15TurnToEarth_001, 2012-079T12:15:00.000
26 *SEQ_VSL_C15TurnToEarth_002, 2012-080T22:15:00.000
27 *SEQ_VSL_C16TurnToEarth_001, 2012-086T12:15:00.000
28 *SEQ_VSL_C16TurnToEarth_002, 2012-087T22:15:00.000
29 *VSL_DLTERM_537, 2012-078T10:25:53.000
30 *VSL_DLTERM_538, 2012-078T14:47:56.000
31 *VSL_DLTERM_539, 2012-078T19:11:36.000
32 *VSL_DLTERM_540, 2012-078T23:37:02.000
33 *VSL_DLTERM_541, 2012-079T03:59:21.000
34 *VSL_DLTERM_574, 2012-085T05:30:59.000
35 *VSL_DLTERM_575, 2012-085T09:53:31.000
36 *VSL_DLTERM_576, 2012-085T14:18:43.000
37 *VSL_DLTERM_577, 2012-085T18:45:45.000
38 *VSL_DLTERM_578, 2012-085T23:09:03.000
39 *EPOCHS_END
40 *Input files used:
41 *File Type  Last modified          File name
42 *****
43 $$EOH
44 $$EOD
45
46 request(VIR_VSL_VMLSTART_S8LAMO,
47         START_TIME,VSL_DLTERM_537-01:16:00,
48         TITLE, "VIR Sequence Start - vir_vsl_S8LAMO (ds096)",
49         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
50         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
51         KEY, "No_Key")
52
53     activity(1,
54             SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
55
56             SEQTRAN_directive(VML_START,2000-001T00:00:00.000,2050-001T00:00:00.000,"ABSLTE","vir_vsl_S8LAMO"
57             fb05")
58         ),
59     note(1,
60         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
61         TEXT,\ "Begin sequence ds096 - vir_vsl_S8LAMO"\
62         ),
63     end;
```

```
63 request(VIR_VSL_C15FullCalibration_001,
64     START_TIME,VSL_DLTERM_537-01:15:00,
65     TITLE, "VIR cooldown and full calibration sequence",
66     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
67     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
68     KEY, "No_Key")
69
70     spawn(1,
71         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
72         REQ_ENGINE_ID,\ANY_ENGINE\,
73         RT_on_board_block(vcfl_vir_calibration_full)
74     ),
75     command(1,
76         SCHEDULED_TIME,\03:30:10\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
77         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C15FullCalibration_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY"\,
78         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
79     ),
80     note(1,
81         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
82         TEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C15FullCalibration_001: Full Calibration VML is finished."\
83     ),
84     note(2,
85         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
86         TEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C15FullCalibration_001: Data Volume in VR4: 0.126 Gibit,120 pages, 15960
87         packets."\
88     end;
89
90 request(VIR_VSL_C15OpenCover_001,
91     START_TIME,VSL_DLTERM_537+02:20:00,
92     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
93     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
94     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
95     KEY, "No_Key")
96
97     activity(1,
98         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
99         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C15OpenCover_001: Set for opening the cover."\,
100        VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
101    ),
102 end;
103
104 request(VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001,
105     START_TIME,VSL_DLTERM_538+00:30:00,
106     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
107     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
108     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
109     KEY, "No_Key")
110
111     command(1,
112         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
113         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
114         detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
115         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR
116     ),
117     command(2,
118         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
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118     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
119     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C150sPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
120     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
121     ),
122     command(3,
123     SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:02:16\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
124     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C150sPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
125     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
126     ),
127     note(1,
128     SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:00:05\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
129     TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C150sPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.043 Gibit\"\\
130     ),
131     command(4,
132     SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:00:01\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
133     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C150sPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
134     detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\"\\,
135     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_Q\",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR
136     ),
137     command(5,
138     SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:00:05\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
139     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
140     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C150sPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
141     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
142     ),
143     command(6,
144     SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:02:16\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
145     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C150sPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
146     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
147     ),
148     note(2,
149     SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:00:05\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
150     TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C150sPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.087 Gibit\"\\
151     ),
152     command(7,
153     SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:00:01\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
154     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C150sPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
155     detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\"\\,
156     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_Q\",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR
157     ),
158     command(8,
159     SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:00:05\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
160     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
161     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C150sPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
162     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
163     ),
164     command(9,
165     SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:02:16\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
166     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C150sPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
167     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
168     ),
169     note(3,
170     SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:00:05\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
171     TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C150sPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.130 Gibit\"\\

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```
172     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
173     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
174     detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
175     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR
176     ),
177     command(11,
178     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
179     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
180     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
181     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
182     ),
183     command(12,
184     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
185     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
186     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
187     ),
188     note(4,
189     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
190     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.174 Gibit"\
191     ),
192     command(13,
193     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
194     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
195     detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
196     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR
197     ),
198     command(14,
199     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
200     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
201     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
202     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
203     ),
204     command(15,
205     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
206     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
207     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
208     ),
209     note(5,
210     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
211     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.217 Gibit"\
212     ),
213     command(16,
214     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
215     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
216     detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
217     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR
218     ),
219     command(17,
220     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
221     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
222     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
223     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
224     ),
225     command(18,
226     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
```

```
224     NTEXT, \ "VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \ ,
225     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
226   ),
227   note(6,
228     SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:00:05 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
229     TEXT, \ "VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.6 Data Volume in MM 0.261 Gibit" \
230   ),
231   command(19,
232     SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:00:01 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
233     NTEXT, \ "VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
234     detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s" \ ,
235     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS( "H_SPE_H_SPA_Q" ,2,49,30,12,44,5,50, "IR_VIS" , "ALL_SUBFRAMES" , "ON" ,10, "NO_VIR
236   ),
237   command(20,
238     SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:00:05 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
239     COMMENT, \ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714" \ ,
240     NTEXT, \ "VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \ ,
241     VIR_SCIENCE( "NO_SEQUENCE" )
242   ),
243   command(21,
244     SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:02:16 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
245     NTEXT, \ "VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \ ,
246     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
247   ),
248   note(7,
249     SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:00:05 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
250     TEXT, \ "VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.7 Data Volume in MM 0.304 Gibit" \
251   ),
252   command(22,
253     SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:00:01 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
254     NTEXT, \ "VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
255     detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s" \ ,
256     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS( "H_SPE_H_SPA_Q" ,2,49,30,12,44,5,50, "IR_VIS" , "ALL_SUBFRAMES" , "ON" ,10, "NO_VIR
257   ),
258   command(23,
259     SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:00:05 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
260     COMMENT, \ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714" \ ,
261     NTEXT, \ "VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \ ,
262     VIR_SCIENCE( "NO_SEQUENCE" )
263   ),
264   command(24,
265     SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:02:16 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
266     NTEXT, \ "VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \ ,
267     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
268   ),
269   note(8,
270     SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:00:05 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
271     TEXT, \ "VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.8 Data Volume in MM 0.348 Gibit" \
272   ),
273   command(25,
274     SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:00:01 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
275     NTEXT, \ "VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
276     detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s" \ ,
277     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS( "H_SPE_H_SPA_Q" ,2,49,30,12,44,5,50, "IR_VIS" , "ALL_SUBFRAMES" , "ON" ,10, "NO_VIR
278   ),
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276     command(26,  
277         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
278         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\",\  
279         NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\",\  
280         VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\"))  
281     ),  
282     command(27,  
283         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
284         NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\  
285         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
286     ),  
287     note(9,  
288         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
289         TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.9 Data Volume in MM 0.391 Gibit\"\  
290     ),  
291     command(28,  
292         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
293         NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2  
294         detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\",  
295         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_Q\",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR  
296     ),  
297     command(29,  
298         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
299         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\",\  
300         NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\",\  
301         VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\"))  
302     ),  
303     command(30,  
304         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
305         NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\  
306         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
307     ),  
308     note(10,  
309         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
310         TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.10 Data Volume in MM 0.435 Gibit\"\  
311     ),  
312     command(31,  
313         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
314         NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2  
315         detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\",  
316         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_Q\",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR  
317     ),  
318     command(32,  
319         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
320         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\",\  
321         NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\",\  
322         VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\"))  
323     ),  
324     command(33,  
325         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
326         NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\  
327         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
328     ),  
329     note(11,  
330         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
331         TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.11 Data Volume in MM 0.478 Gibit\"
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330     ),
331     command(34,
332         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
333         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
334         detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
335         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR
336     ),
337     command(35,
338         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
339         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
340         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
341         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
342     ),
343     command(36,
344         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
345         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
346         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
347     ),
348     note(12,
349         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
350         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.12 Data Volume in MM 0.522 Gibit"\,
351     ),
352     command(37,
353         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
354         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
355         detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
356         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR
357     ),
358     command(38,
359         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
360         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
361         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
362         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
363     ),
364     command(39,
365         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
366         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
367         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
368     ),
369     note(13,
370         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
371         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.13 Data Volume in MM 0.565 Gibit"\,
372     ),
373     command(40,
374         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
375         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
376         detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
377         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR
378     ),
379     command(41,
380         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
381         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
382         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
383         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
384     ),
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382     command(42,  
383         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
384         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,  
385         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
386     ),  
387     note(14,  
388         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
389         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.14 Data Volume in MM 0.609 Gibit\"\\  
390     ),  
391     command(43,  
392         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
393         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2  
394         detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\"\\,  
395         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_Q\",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR  
396     ),  
397     command(44,  
398         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
399         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,  
400         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,  
401         VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")  
402     ),  
403     command(45,  
404         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
405         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,  
406         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
407     ),  
408     note(15,  
409         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
410         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.15 Data Volume in MM 0.652 Gibit\"\\  
411     ),  
412     command(46,  
413         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
414         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2  
415         detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\"\\,  
416         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_Q\",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR  
417     ),  
418     command(47,  
419         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
420         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,  
421         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,  
422         VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")  
423     ),  
424     command(48,  
425         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
426         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,  
427         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
428     ),  
429     note(16,  
430         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
431         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.16 Data Volume in MM 0.696 Gibit\"\\  
432     ),  
433     end;  
434     request(VIR_VSL_C15DumpDataToVR4_001,  
435         START_TIME,VSL_DLTERM_538+01:10:00,  
436         TITLE, \"VIR dump data into VR4\",
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436     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
437     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
438     KEY, "No_Key")
439
440     command(1,
441         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
442         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15DumpDataToVR4_001: begin data dumping into VR4.\"\\,
443         VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
444     ),
445     command(2,
446         SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:19:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
447         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15DumpDataToVR4_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
448         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
449     ),
450     note(1,
451         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
452         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15DumpDataToVR4_001: data volume in VR4 0.635 Gibit.\"\\
453     ),
454 end;
455
456 request(VIR_VSL_C15PushBroomToVIR_002,
457     START_TIME,VSL_DLTERM_539+01:25:00,
458     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
459     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
460     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
461     KEY, "No_Key")
462
463     command(1,
464         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
465         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15PushBroomToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
466         frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
467         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VI
468     ),
469     command(2,
470         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
471         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
472         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15PushBroomToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
473         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
474     ),
475     command(3,
476         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
477         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15PushBroomToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
478         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
479     ),
480     note(1,
481         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
482         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15PushBroomToVIR_002: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.174 Gibit\"\\
483     ),
484     command(4,
485         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
486         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15PushBroomToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
487         frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
488         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VI
489     ),
490     command(5,
491         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
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490     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
491     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15PushBroomToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
492     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
493   ),
494   command(6,
495     SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:05:36\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
496     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15PushBroomToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
497     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
498   ),
499   note(2,
500     SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:00:05\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
501     TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15PushBroomToVIR_002: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.348 Gibit\"\\
502   ),
503   command(7,
504     SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:00:01\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
505     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15PushBroomToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
506     frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
507     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VI
508   ),
509     command(8,
510     SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:00:05\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
511     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
512     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15PushBroomToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
513     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
514   ),
515     command(9,
516     SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:05:36\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
517     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15PushBroomToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
518     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
519   ),
520     note(3,
521     SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:00:05\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
522     TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15PushBroomToVIR_002: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.522 Gibit\"\\
523   ),
524     command(10,
525     SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:00:01\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
526     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15PushBroomToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
527     frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
528     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VI
529   ),
530     command(11,
531     SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:00:05\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
532     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
533     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15PushBroomToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
534     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
535   ),
536     command(12,
537     SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:05:36\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
538     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15PushBroomToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
539     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
540   ),
541     note(4,
542     SCHEDULED_TIME,\"00:00:05\",FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
543     TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15PushBroomToVIR_002: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.696 Gibit\"\\
544   ),
545   end;
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544
545 request(VIR_VSL_C15DumpDataToVR4_002,
546         START_TIME,VSL_DLTERM_539+01:55:00,
547         TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
548         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
549         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
550         KEY, "No_Key")
551
552     command(1,
553         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
554         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C15DumpDataToVR4_002: begin data dumping into VR4."\,
555         VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
556     ),
557     command(2,
558         SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:19:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
559         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C15DumpDataToVR4_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
560         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
561     ),
562     note(1,
563         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
564         TEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C15DumpDataToVR4_002: data volume in VR4 1.145 Gibit."\
565     ),
566 end;
567
568 request(VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003,
569         START_TIME,VSL_DLTERM_540+00:55:00,
570         TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
571         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
572         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
573         KEY, "No_Key")
574
575     command(1,
576         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
577         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
578         detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
579         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50, "IR_VIS", "ALL_SUBFRAMES", "ON",10, "NO_VIR
580     ),
581     command(2,
582         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
583         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
584         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
585         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
586     ),
587     command(3,
588         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
589         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\,
590         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
591     ),
592     note(1,
593         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
594         TEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.043 Gibit"\
595     ),
596     command(4,
597         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
598         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
599         detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
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598     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR
599     ),
600     command(5,
601     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
602     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
603     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
604     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
605     ),
606     command(6,
607     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
608     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
609     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
610     ),
611     note(2,
612     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
613     TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.087 Gibit\"\\
614     ),
615     command(7,
616     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
617     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
        detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\"\\,
618     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR
619     ),
620     command(8,
621     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
622     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
623     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
624     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
625     ),
626     command(9,
627     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
628     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
629     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
630     ),
631     note(3,
632     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
633     TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.130 Gibit\"\\
634     ),
635     command(10,
636     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
637     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
        detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\"\\,
638     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR
639     ),
640     command(11,
641     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
642     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
643     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
644     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
645     ),
646     command(12,
647     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
648     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
649     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
650     ),
```

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651     note(4,  
652         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
653         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.174 Gibit"\  
654     ),  
655     command(13,  
656         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
657         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2  
        detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\  
658         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR  
659     ),  
660     command(14,  
661         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
662         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\  
663         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\  
664         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")  
665     ),  
666     command(15,  
667         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
668         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\  
669         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
670     ),  
671     note(5,  
672         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
673         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.217 Gibit"\  
674     ),  
675     command(16,  
676         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
677         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2  
        detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\  
678         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR  
679     ),  
680     command(17,  
681         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
682         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\  
683         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\  
684         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")  
685     ),  
686     command(18,  
687         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
688         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\  
689         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
690     ),  
691     note(6,  
692         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
693         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.6 Data Volume in MM 0.261 Gibit"\  
694     ),  
695     command(19,  
696         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
697         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2  
        detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\  
698         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR  
699     ),  
700     command(20,  
701         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
702         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\  

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703     NTEXT, \ "VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \ ,
704     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
705   ),
706   command(21,
707     SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:02:16 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
708     NTEXT, \ "VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \ ,
709     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
710   ),
711   note(7,
712     SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:00:05 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
713     TEXT, \ "VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.7 Data Volume in MM 0.304 Gibit" \
714   ),
715   command(22,
716     SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:00:01 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
717     NTEXT, \ "VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
718     detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s" \ ,
719     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q", 2, 49, 30, 12, 44, 5, 50, "IR_VIS", "ALL_SUBFRAMES", "ON", 10, "NO_VIR
720   ),
721   command(23,
722     SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:00:05 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
723     COMMENT, \ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714" \ ,
724     NTEXT, \ "VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \ ,
725     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
726   ),
727   command(24,
728     SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:02:16 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
729     NTEXT, \ "VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \ ,
730     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
731   ),
732   note(8,
733     SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:00:05 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
734     TEXT, \ "VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.8 Data Volume in MM 0.348 Gibit" \
735   ),
736   command(25,
737     SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:00:01 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
738     NTEXT, \ "VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
739     detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s" \ ,
740     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q", 2, 49, 30, 12, 44, 5, 50, "IR_VIS", "ALL_SUBFRAMES", "ON", 10, "NO_VIR
741   ),
742   command(26,
743     SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:00:05 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
744     COMMENT, \ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714" \ ,
745     NTEXT, \ "VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \ ,
746     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
747   ),
748   command(27,
749     SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:02:16 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
750     NTEXT, \ "VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \ ,
751     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
752   ),
753   note(9,
754     SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:00:05 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
755     TEXT, \ "VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.9 Data Volume in MM 0.391 Gibit" \
756   ),
757   command(28,
758     SCHEDULED_TIME, \ 00:00:01 \ , FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
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757 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
758 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR
759 ),
760 command(29,
761 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
762 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
763 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
764 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
765 ),
766 command(30,
767 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
768 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
769 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
770 ),
771 note(10,
772 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
773 TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.10 Data Volume in MM 0.435 Gibit"\
774 ),
775 command(31,
776 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
777 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
778 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR
779 ),
780 command(32,
781 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
782 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
783 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
784 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
785 ),
786 command(33,
787 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
788 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
789 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
790 ),
791 note(11,
792 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
793 TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.11 Data Volume in MM 0.478 Gibit"\
794 ),
795 command(34,
796 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
797 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
798 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR
799 ),
800 command(35,
801 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
802 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
803 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
804 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
805 ),
806 command(36,
807 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
808 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
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809     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
810   ),
811   note(12,
812     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
813     TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.12 Data Volume in MM 0.522 Gibit\"
814   ),
815   command(37,
816     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
817     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
      detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\",
818     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR
819   ),
820   command(38,
821     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
822     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\",
823     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\",
824     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
825   ),
826   command(39,
827     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
828     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"
829     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
830   ),
831   note(13,
832     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
833     TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.13 Data Volume in MM 0.565 Gibit\"
834   ),
835   command(40,
836     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
837     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
      detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\",
838     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR
839   ),
840   command(41,
841     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
842     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\",
843     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\",
844     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
845   ),
846   command(42,
847     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
848     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"
849     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
850   ),
851   note(14,
852     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
853     TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.14 Data Volume in MM 0.609 Gibit\"
854   ),
855   command(43,
856     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
857     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
      detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\",
858     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR
859   ),
860   command(44,
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861     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
862     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
863     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
864     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
865   ),
866   command(45,
867     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
868     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
869     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
870   ),
871   note(15,
872     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
873     TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.15 Data Volume in MM 0.652 Gibit\"\\
874   ),
875   command(46,
876     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
877     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
      detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\"\\,
878     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_Q\",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR
879   ),
880   command(47,
881     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
882     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
883     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
884     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
885   ),
886   command(48,
887     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
888     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
889     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
890   ),
891   note(16,
892     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
893     TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.16 Data Volume in MM 0.696 Gibit\"\\
894   ),
895 end;
896
897 request(VIR_VSL_C15DumpDataToVR4_003,
898   START_TIME,VSL_DLTERM_540+01:35:00,
899   TITLE, \"VIR dump data into VR4\",
900   REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
901   PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
902   KEY, \"No_Key\")
903
904   command(1,
905     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
906     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15DumpDataToVR4_003: begin data dumping into VR4.\"\\,
907     VIR_MM_DUMP(\"LOSSLESS\")
908   ),
909   command(2,
910     SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:19:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
911     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15DumpDataToVR4_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
912     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
913   ),
914   note(1,
915     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
916     TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15DumpDataToVR4_003: data volume in VR4 1.655 Gibit.\"\\
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917     ),
918 end;
919
920 request(VIR_VSL_C15PushBroomToVIR_004,
921         START_TIME,VSL_DLTERM_541+01:24:00,
922         TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
923         REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
924         PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
925         KEY, "No_Key")
926
927     command(1,
928         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
929         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C15PushBroomToVIR_004: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
          frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
930
          VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VI
931     ),
932     command(2,
933         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
934         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
935         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C15PushBroomToVIR_004: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
936         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
937     ),
938     command(3,
939         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
940         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C15PushBroomToVIR_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
941         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
942     ),
943     note(1,
944         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
945         TEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C15PushBroomToVIR_004: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.174 Gibit"\
946     ),
947     command(4,
948         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
949         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C15PushBroomToVIR_004: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
          frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
950
          VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VI
951     ),
952     command(5,
953         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
954         COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
955         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C15PushBroomToVIR_004: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
956         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
957     ),
958     command(6,
959         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
960         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C15PushBroomToVIR_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.""\,
961         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
962     ),
963     note(2,
964         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
965         TEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C15PushBroomToVIR_004: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.348 Gibit"\
966     ),
967     command(7,
968         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
969         NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C15PushBroomToVIR_004: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
          frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\,
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970     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VI
971 ),
972     command(8,
973     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
974     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
975     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15PushBroomToVIR_004: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
976     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
977 ),
978     command(9,
979     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
980     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15PushBroomToVIR_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
981     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
982 ),
983     note(3,
984     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
985     TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15PushBroomToVIR_004: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.522 Gibit\"\\
986 ),
987     command(10,
988     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
989     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15PushBroomToVIR_004: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
990     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VI
991 ),
992     command(11,
993     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
994     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
995     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15PushBroomToVIR_004: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
996     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
997 ),
998     command(12,
999     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1000     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15PushBroomToVIR_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1001     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1002 ),
1003     note(4,
1004     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1005     TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15PushBroomToVIR_004: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.696 Gibit\"\\
1006 ),
1007 end;
1008
1009 request(VIR_VSL_C15CryocoolerOff_001,
1010     START_TIME,VSL_DLTERM_541+01:52:00,
1011     TITLE, \"VIR cryocooler off\",
1012     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
1013     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
1014     KEY, \"No_Key\")
1015
1016     command(1,
1017     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1018     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15CryocoolerOff_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1019     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1020 ),
1021     command(2,
1022     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1023     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C15CryocoolerOff_001: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime.\"\\,
1024     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN(\"OFF\",75,2500)
```

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1025     ),
1026     note(1,
1027         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1028         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15CryocoolerOff_001: the cryocooling is off.\"\
1029     ),
1030 end;
1031
1032 request(VIR_VSL_C15CloseCover_001,
1033     START_TIME,VSL_DLTERM_541+02:25:00,
1034     TITLE, \"VIR close cover\",
1035     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
1036     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
1037     KEY, \"No_Key\")
1038
1039     activity(1,
1040         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1041         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15CloseCover_001: Set for closing the cover.\"\,
1042         VIR_Cover(vir_cover,\"CLOSE\")
1043     ),
1044 end;
1045
1046 request(VIR_VSL_C15DumpDataToVR4_004,
1047     START_TIME,VSL_DLTERM_541+02:27:00,
1048     TITLE, \"VIR dump data into VR4\",
1049     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
1050     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
1051     KEY, \"No_Key\")
1052
1053     command(1,
1054         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1055         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15DumpDataToVR4_004: begin data dumping into VR4.\"\,
1056         VIR_MM_DUMP(\"LOSSLESS\")
1057     ),
1058     command(2,
1059         SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:19:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1060         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15DumpDataToVR4_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\,
1061         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1062     ),
1063     note(1,
1064         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1065         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15DumpDataToVR4_004: data volume in VR4 2.165 Gibit.\"\
1066     ),
1067 end;
1068
1069 request(VIR_VSL_C15SAFEmode_001,
1070     START_TIME,VSL_DLTERM_541+03:47:00,
1071     TITLE, \"VIR Safe\",
1072     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
1073     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
1074     KEY, \"No_Key\")
1075
1076     command(1,
1077         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1078         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15SAFEmode_001: changing VIR mode into SAFE\"\,
1079         VIR_SAFE()
1080     ),
1081     command(2,
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1082     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:01:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1083     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15SAFEmode_001: dump the error log information"\,
1084     VIR_TC_ERROR_LOG("DUMP_LOG")
1085     ),
1086     note(1,
1087     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:01:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1088     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C15SAFEmode_001: VIR is in SAFE mode and error log produced"\
1089     ),
1090 end;
1091
1092 request(VIR_VSL_C16Cryocooler0n_001,
1093     START_TIME,VSL_DLTERM_575-05:02:32,
1094     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler on",
1095     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1096     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1097     KEY, "No_Key")
1098
1099     command(1,
1100     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1101     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16Cryocooler0n_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
1102     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1103     ),
1104     command(2,
1105     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1106     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16Cryocooler0n_001: changing VIR mode into COOLDOWN."\",
1107     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("CLOSELOOP",75,0)
1108     ),
1109     note(1,
1110     SCHEDULED_TIME,\02:59:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1111     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16Cryocooler0n_001: VIR autonomously transitioned to STAND_BY mode after 3 hour
1112     waiting."\"
1113     ),
1114 end;
1115
1115 request(VIR_VSL_C160penCover_001,
1116     START_TIME,VSL_DLTERM_574+02:20:00,
1117     TITLE, "VIR open cover",
1118     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1119     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1120     KEY, "No_Key")
1121
1122     command(1,
1123     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1124     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C160penCover_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY"\",
1125     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1126     ),
1127     activity(1,
1128     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1129     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C160penCover_001: Set for opening the cover."\",
1130     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"OPEN")
1131     ),
1132 end;
1133
1134 request(VIR_VSL_C160sPushBroomToVIR_001,
1135     START_TIME,VSL_DLTERM_575+00:30:00,
1136     TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
1137     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
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1138     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1139     KEY, "No_Key")
1140
1141     command(1,
1142     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1143     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
1144     detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
1145     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR
1146     ),
1147     command(2,
1148     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1149     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1150     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1151     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1152     ),
1153     command(3,
1154     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1155     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
1156     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1157     ),
1158     note(1,
1159     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1160     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.043 Gibit"\
1161     ),
1162     command(4,
1163     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1164     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
1165     detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
1166     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR
1167     ),
1168     command(5,
1169     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1170     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1171     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1172     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1173     ),
1174     command(6,
1175     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1176     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
1177     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1178     ),
1179     note(2,
1180     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1181     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.087 Gibit"\
1182     ),
1183     command(7,
1184     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1185     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
1186     detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
1187     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR
1188     ),
1189     command(8,
1190     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1191     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1192     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
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1190     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1191   ),
1192   command(9,
1193     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1194     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
1195     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1196   ),
1197   note(3,
1198     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1199     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.130 Gibit" \
1200   ),
1201   command(10,
1202     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1203     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
1204     detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s" \,
1205     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR
1206   ),
1207   command(11,
1208     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1209     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714" \,
1210     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \,
1211     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1212   ),
1213   command(12,
1214     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1215     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
1216     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1217   ),
1218   note(4,
1219     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1220     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.174 Gibit" \
1221   ),
1222   command(13,
1223     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1224     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
1225     detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s" \,
1226     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR
1227   ),
1228   command(14,
1229     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1230     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714" \,
1231     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode" \,
1232     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1233   ),
1234   command(15,
1235     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1236     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
1237     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1238   ),
1239   note(5,
1240     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1241     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.217 Gibit" \
1242   ),
1243   command(16,
1244     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
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1243 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
1244 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR
1245 ),
1246 command(17,
1247 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1248 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1249 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1250 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1251 ),
1252 command(18,
1253 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1254 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
1255 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1256 ),
1257 note(6,
1258 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1259 TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.6 Data Volume in MM 0.261 Gibit"\
1260 ),
1261 command(19,
1262 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1263 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
1264 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR
1265 ),
1266 command(20,
1267 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1268 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1269 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1270 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1271 ),
1272 command(21,
1273 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1274 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
1275 VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1276 ),
1277 note(7,
1278 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1279 TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.7 Data Volume in MM 0.304 Gibit"\
1280 ),
1281 command(22,
1282 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1283 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
1284 VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR
1285 ),
1286 command(23,
1287 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1288 COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1289 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1290 VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1291 ),
1292 command(24,
1293 SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1294 NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
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1295     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1296   ),
1297   note(8,
1298     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1299     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.8 Data Volume in MM 0.348 Gibit"\
1300   ),
1301   command(25,
1302     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1303     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
1304       detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
1305     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR
1306   ),
1307   command(26,
1308     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1309     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1310     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1311     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1312   ),
1313   command(27,
1314     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1315     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
1316     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1317   ),
1318   note(9,
1319     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1320     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.9 Data Volume in MM 0.391 Gibit"\
1321   ),
1322   command(28,
1323     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1324     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
1325       detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
1326     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR
1327   ),
1328   command(29,
1329     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1330     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1331     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1332     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1333   ),
1334   command(30,
1335     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1336     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
1337     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1338   ),
1339   note(10,
1340     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1341     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.10 Data Volume in MM 0.435 Gibit"\
1342   ),
1343   command(31,
1344     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1345     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
1346       detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
1347     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR
1348   ),
1349   command(32,
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1347     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1348     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
1349     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1350     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
1351   ),
1352   command(33,
1353     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1354     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1355     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1356   ),
1357   note(11,
1358     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1359     TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.11 Data Volume in MM 0.478 Gibit\"\\
1360   ),
1361   command(34,
1362     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1363     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
1364     detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\"\\,
1365     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_Q\",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR
1366   ),
1367   command(35,
1368     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1369     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
1370     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1371     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
1372   ),
1373   command(36,
1374     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1375     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1376     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1377   ),
1378   note(12,
1379     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1380     TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.12 Data Volume in MM 0.522 Gibit\"\\
1381   ),
1382   command(37,
1383     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1384     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
1385     detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\"\\,
1386     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_Q\",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR
1387   ),
1388   command(38,
1389     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1390     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
1391     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1392     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
1393   ),
1394   command(39,
1395     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1396     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1397     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1398   ),
1399   note(13,
1400     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1401     TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.13 Data Volume in MM 0.565 Gibit\"\\
1402   ),
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1401     command(40,
1402         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1403         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
1404         detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
1405         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR
1406     ),
1407     command(41,
1408         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1409         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1410         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1411         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1412     ),
1413     command(42,
1414         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1415         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
1416         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1417     ),
1418     note(14,
1419         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1420         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.14 Data Volume in MM 0.609 Gibit"\
1421     ),
1422     command(43,
1423         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1424         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
1425         detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
1426         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR
1427     ),
1428     command(44,
1429         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1430         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1431         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1432         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1433     ),
1434     command(45,
1435         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1436         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
1437         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1438     ),
1439     note(15,
1440         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1441         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.15 Data Volume in MM 0.652 Gibit"\
1442     ),
1443     command(46,
1444         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1445         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
1446         detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
1447         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR
1448     ),
1449     command(47,
1450         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1451         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1452         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1453         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1454     ),
1455     command(48,
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1453     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1454     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1455     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1456   ),
1457   note(16,
1458     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1459     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_001: Cube N.16 Data Volume in MM 0.696 Gibit\"\\
1460   ),
1461 end;
1462
1463 request(VIR_VSL_C16DumpDataToVR4_001,
1464   START_TIME,VSL_DLTERM_575+01:10:00,
1465   TITLE, \"VIR dump data into VR4\",
1466   REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
1467   PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
1468   KEY, \"No_Key\")
1469
1470   command(1,
1471     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1472     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16DumpDataToVR4_001: begin data dumping into VR4.\"\\,
1473     VIR_MM_DUMP(\"LOSSLESS\")
1474   ),
1475   command(2,
1476     SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:19:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1477     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16DumpDataToVR4_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1478     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1479   ),
1480   note(1,
1481     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1482     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16DumpDataToVR4_001: data volume in VR4 0.510 Gibit.\"\\
1483   ),
1484 end;
1485
1486 request(VIR_VSL_C16PushBroomToVIR_002,
1487   START_TIME,VSL_DLTERM_576+01:25:00,
1488   TITLE, \"VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.\",
1489   REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
1490   PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
1491   KEY, \"No_Key\")
1492
1493   command(1,
1494     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1495     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16PushBroomToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
1496     frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
1497     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\", \"ALL_SUBFRAMES\", \"ON\", 10, \"NO_VI
1498   ),
1499   command(2,
1500     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1501     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
1502     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16PushBroomToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1503     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
1504   ),
1505   command(3,
1506     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1507     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16PushBroomToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1508     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1509   ),
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1509     note(1,
1510         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1511         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16PushBroomToVIR_002: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.174 Gibit\"\\
1512     ),
1513     command(4,
1514         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1515         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16PushBroomToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
1516         frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
1517         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VI
1518     ),
1519     command(5,
1520         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1521         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
1522         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16PushBroomToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1523         VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
1524     ),
1525     command(6,
1526         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1527         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16PushBroomToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1528         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1529     ),
1530     note(2,
1531         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1532         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16PushBroomToVIR_002: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.348 Gibit\"\\
1533     ),
1534     command(7,
1535         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1536         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16PushBroomToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
1537         frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
1538         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VI
1539     ),
1540     command(8,
1541         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1542         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
1543         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16PushBroomToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1544         VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
1545     ),
1546     command(9,
1547         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1548         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16PushBroomToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1549         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1550     ),
1551     note(3,
1552         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1553         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16PushBroomToVIR_002: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.522 Gibit\"\\
1554     ),
1555     command(10,
1556         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1557         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16PushBroomToVIR_002: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
1558         frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
1559         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VI
1560     ),
1561     command(11,
1562         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1563         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
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1561     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C16PushBroomToVIR_002: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1562     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1563   ),
1564   command(12,
1565     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1566     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C16PushBroomToVIR_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
1567     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1568   ),
1569   note(4,
1570     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1571     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C16PushBroomToVIR_002: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.696 Gibit"\
1572   ),
1573 end;
1574
1575 request(VIR_VSL_C16DumpDataToVR4_002,
1576   START_TIME,VSL_DLTERM_576+01:55:00,
1577   TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
1578   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1579   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1580   KEY, "No_Key")
1581
1582   command(1,
1583     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1584     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C16DumpDataToVR4_002: begin data dumping into VR4."\",
1585     VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
1586   ),
1587   command(2,
1588     SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:19:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1589     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C16DumpDataToVR4_002: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\",
1590     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1591   ),
1592   note(1,
1593     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1594     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C16DumpDataToVR4_002: data volume in VR4 1.019 Gibit."\"
1595   ),
1596 end;
1597
1598 request(VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003,
1599   START_TIME,VSL_DLTERM_577+00:55:00,
1600   TITLE, "VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.",
1601   REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
1602   PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
1603   KEY, "No_Key")
1604
1605   command(1,
1606     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1607     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
1608     detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\,
1609     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50, "IR_VIS", "ALL_SUBFRAMES", "ON", 10, "NO_VIR
1610   ),
1611   command(2,
1612     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1613     COMMENT,\ "COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\,
1614     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\,
1615     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1616   ),
1617   command(3,

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1617     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1618     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1619     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1620   ),
1621   note(1,
1622     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1623     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.043 Gibit\"\\
1624   ),
1625   command(4,
1626     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1627     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
1628     detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\"\\,
1629     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_Q\",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR
1630   ),
1631   command(5,
1632     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1633     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
1634     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1635     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
1636   ),
1637   command(6,
1638     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1639     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1640     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1641   ),
1642   note(2,
1643     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1644     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.087 Gibit\"\\
1645   ),
1646   command(7,
1647     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1648     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
1649     detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\"\\,
1650     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_Q\",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR
1651   ),
1652   command(8,
1653     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1654     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
1655     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1656     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
1657   ),
1658   command(9,
1659     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1660     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1661     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1662   ),
1663   note(3,
1664     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1665     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.130 Gibit\"\\
1666   ),
1667   command(10,
1668     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1669     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
1670     detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\"\\,
1671     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_Q\",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR
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1669     ),
1670     command(11,
1671         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1672         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\",\
1673         NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\",\
1674         VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
1675     ),
1676     command(12,
1677         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1678         NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\",
1679         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1680     ),
1681     note(4,
1682         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1683         TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.174 Gibit\",\
1684     ),
1685     command(13,
1686         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1687         NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
1688         detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\",\
1689         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_Q\",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR
1690     ),
1691     command(14,
1692         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1693         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\",\
1694         NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\",\
1695         VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
1696     ),
1697     command(15,
1698         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1699         NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\",
1700         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1701     ),
1702     note(5,
1703         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1704         TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.5 Data Volume in MM 0.217 Gibit\",\
1705     ),
1706     command(16,
1707         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1708         NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
1709         detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\",\
1710         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_Q\",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR
1711     ),
1712     command(17,
1713         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1714         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\",\
1715         NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\",\
1716         VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
1717     ),
1718     command(18,
1719         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1720         NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\",
1721         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1722     ),
1723     note(6,
1724         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
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1723     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.6 Data Volume in MM 0.261 Gibit"\  
1724     ),  
1725     command(19,  
1726     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1727     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2  
     detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\  
1728     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR  
1729     ),  
1730     command(20,  
1731     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1732     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\  
1733     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\  
1734     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")  
1735     ),  
1736     command(21,  
1737     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1738     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\  
1739     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
1740     ),  
1741     note(7,  
1742     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1743     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.7 Data Volume in MM 0.304 Gibit"\  
1744     ),  
1745     command(22,  
1746     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1747     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2  
     detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\  
1748     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR  
1749     ),  
1750     command(23,  
1751     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1752     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\  
1753     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\  
1754     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")  
1755     ),  
1756     command(24,  
1757     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1758     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\  
1759     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
1760     ),  
1761     note(8,  
1762     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1763     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.8 Data Volume in MM 0.348 Gibit"\  
1764     ),  
1765     command(25,  
1766     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1767     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2  
     detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\  
1768     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR  
1769     ),  
1770     command(26,  
1771     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1772     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\  
1773     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\  
1774     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
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1775     ),
1776     command(27,
1777         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1778         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1779         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1780     ),
1781     note(9,
1782         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1783         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.9 Data Volume in MM 0.391 Gibit\"\\
1784     ),
1785     command(28,
1786         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1787         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
1788         detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\"\\,
1789         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_Q\",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR
1790     ),
1791     command(29,
1792         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1793         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
1794         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1795         VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
1796     ),
1797     command(30,
1798         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1799         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1800         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1801     ),
1802     note(10,
1803         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1804         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.10 Data Volume in MM 0.435 Gibit\"\\
1805     ),
1806     command(31,
1807         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1808         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
1809         detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\"\\,
1810         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_Q\",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\",\"ON\",10,\"NO_VIR
1811     ),
1812     command(32,
1813         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1814         COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
1815         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1816         VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
1817     ),
1818     command(33,
1819         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1820         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1821         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1822     ),
1823     note(11,
1824         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1825         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.11 Data Volume in MM 0.478 Gibit\"\\
1826     ),
1827     command(34,
1828         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1829         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
1830         detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\"\\,
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1828     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR
1829 ),
1830     command(35,
1831     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1832     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
1833     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1834     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1835     ),
1836     command(36,
1837     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1838     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1839     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1840     ),
1841     note(12,
1842     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1843     TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.12 Data Volume in MM 0.522 Gibit\"\\
1844     ),
1845     command(37,
1846     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1847     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
1848     detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\"\\,
1849     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR
1850     ),
1851     command(38,
1852     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1853     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
1854     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1855     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1856     ),
1857     command(39,
1858     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1859     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1860     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1861     ),
1862     note(13,
1863     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1864     TEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.13 Data Volume in MM 0.565 Gibit\"\\
1865     ),
1866     command(40,
1867     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1868     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2
1869     detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s\"\\,
1870     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR
1871     ),
1872     command(41,
1873     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1874     COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
1875     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1876     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
1877     ),
1878     command(42,
1879     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1880     NTEXT,\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1881     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1882     ),
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1881     note(14,  
1882         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1883         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.14 Data Volume in MM 0.609 Gibit"\  
1884     ),  
1885     command(43,  
1886         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1887         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2  
            detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\  
1888         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR  
1889     ),  
1890     command(44,  
1891         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1892         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\  
1893         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\  
1894         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")  
1895     ),  
1896     command(45,  
1897         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1898         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\  
1899         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
1900     ),  
1901     note(15,  
1902         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1903         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.15 Data Volume in MM 0.652 Gibit"\  
1904     ),  
1905     command(46,  
1906         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1907         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_Q,2  
            detector,50 frame,2 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=0.9s"\  
1908         VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_Q",2,49,30,12,44,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VIR  
1909     ),  
1910     command(47,  
1911         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1912         COMMENT,\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\  
1913         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\  
1914         VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")  
1915     ),  
1916     command(48,  
1917         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:02:16\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1918         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\  
1919         VIR_TC_STAND_BY()  
1920     ),  
1921     note(16,  
1922         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
1923         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16QsPushBroomToVIR_003: Cube N.16 Data Volume in MM 0.696 Gibit"\  
1924     ),  
1925 end;  
1926  
1927 request(VIR_VSL_C16DumpDataToVR4_003,  
1928     START_TIME,VSL_DLTERM_577+01:35:00,  
1929     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",  
1930     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
1931     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
1932     KEY, "No_Key")  
1933  
1934     command(1,
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1935     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1936     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16DumpDataToVR4_003: begin data dumping into VR4.\"\\,
1937     VIR_MM_DUMP(\"LOSSLESS\")
1938     ),
1939     command(2,
1940     SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:19:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1941     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16DumpDataToVR4_003: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1942     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1943     ),
1944     note(1,
1945     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1946     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16DumpDataToVR4_003: data volume in VR4 1.529 Gibit.\"\\
1947     ),
1948 end;
1949
1950 request(VIR_VSL_C16PushBroomToVIR_004,
1951     START_TIME,VSL_DLTERM_578+01:25:00,
1952     TITLE, \"VIR science acquisition, Mass Memories storing.\",
1953     REQUESTOR, \"sfonte\",
1954     PROCESSOR, \"GSC1\",
1955     KEY, \"No_Key\")
1956
1957     command(1,
1958     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
1959     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16PushBroomToVIR_004: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
1960     frame,6 RepTime,Integratation time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
1961     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\", \"ON\",10,\"NO_VI
1962     ),
1963     command(2,
1964     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1965     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
1966     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16PushBroomToVIR_004: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1967     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
1968     ),
1969     command(3,
1970     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1971     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16PushBroomToVIR_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY.\"\\,
1972     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1973     ),
1974     note(1,
1975     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1976     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16PushBroomToVIR_004: Cube N.1 Data Volume in MM 0.174 Gibit\"\\
1977     ),
1978     command(4,
1979     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1980     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16PushBroomToVIR_004: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
1981     frame,6 RepTime,Integratation time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s\"\\,
1982     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS(\"H_SPE_H_SPA_F\",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,\"IR_VIS\",\"ALL_SUBFRAMES\", \"ON\",10,\"NO_VI
1983     ),
1984     command(5,
1985     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1986     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714\"\\,
1987     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16PushBroomToVIR_004: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode\"\\,
1988     VIR_SCIENCE(\"NO_SEQUENCE\")
1989     ),
1990     command(6,

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1989     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1990     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16PushBroomToVIR_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
1991     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
1992     ),
1993     note(2,
1994     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1995     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16PushBroomToVIR_004: Cube N.2 Data Volume in MM 0.348 Gibit"\\
1996     ),
1997     command(7,
1998     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
1999     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16PushBroomToVIR_004: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
        frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\\,
2000     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VI
2001     ),
2002     command(8,
2003     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2004     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\\,
2005     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16PushBroomToVIR_004: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\\,
2006     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
2007     ),
2008     command(9,
2009     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2010     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16PushBroomToVIR_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
2011     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2012     ),
2013     note(3,
2014     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2015     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16PushBroomToVIR_004: Cube N.3 Data Volume in MM 0.522 Gibit"\\
2016     ),
2017     command(10,
2018     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2019     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16PushBroomToVIR_004: Set VIR science parameters: H_SPE_H_SPA_F,2 detector,50
        frame,6 RepTime,Integration time IR=0.6s VIS=3.5s"\\,
2020     VIR_TC_SCIENCE_PARAMS("H_SPE_H_SPA_F",6,49,30,77,175,5,50,"IR_VIS","ALL_SUBFRAMES","ON",10,"NO_VI
2021     ),
2022     command(11,
2023     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2024     COMMENT,\\"COMPRESSION_RATIO=0.714"\\,
2025     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16PushBroomToVIR_004: Acquire science data and return to STAND BY mode"\\,
2026     VIR_SCIENCE("NO_SEQUENCE")
2027     ),
2028     command(12,
2029     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:05:36\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2030     NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16PushBroomToVIR_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY."\\,
2031     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2032     ),
2033     note(4,
2034     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2035     TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16PushBroomToVIR_004: Cube N.4 Data Volume in MM 0.696 Gibit"\\
2036     ),
2037 end;
2038
2039 request(VIR_VSL_C16Cryocooler0ff_001,
2040     START_TIME,VSL_DLTERM_578+01:53:00,
2041     TITLE, "VIR cryocooler off",
2042     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",

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2043     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
2044     KEY, "No_Key")
2045
2046     command(1,
2047     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
2048     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C16CryocoolerOff_001: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
2049     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2050     ),
2051     command(2,
2052     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2053     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C16CryocoolerOff_001: Turn Off cryocooler to preserve lifetime." \,
2054     VIR_TC_COOL_DOWN("OFF",75,2500)
2055     ),
2056     note(1,
2057     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:01\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2058     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C16CryocoolerOff_001: the cryocooling is off." \
2059     ),
2060 end;
2061
2062 request(VIR_VSL_C16CloseCover_007,
2063     START_TIME,VSL_DLTERM_578+02:25:00,
2064     TITLE, "VIR close cover",
2065     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
2066     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
2067     KEY, "No_Key")
2068
2069     activity(1,
2070     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
2071     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C16CloseCover_007: Set for closing the cover." \,
2072     VIR_Cover(vir_cover,"CLOSE")
2073     ),
2074 end;
2075
2076 request(VIR_VSL_C16DumpDataToVR4_004,
2077     START_TIME,VSL_DLTERM_578+02:27:00,
2078     TITLE, "VIR dump data into VR4",
2079     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",
2080     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",
2081     KEY, "No_Key")
2082
2083     command(1,
2084     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,
2085     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C16DumpDataToVR4_004: begin data dumping into VR4." \,
2086     VIR_MM_DUMP("LOSSLESS")
2087     ),
2088     command(2,
2089     SCHEDULED_TIME,\01:19:55\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2090     NTEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C16DumpDataToVR4_004: changing VIR mode into STAND_BY." \,
2091     VIR_TC_STAND_BY()
2092     ),
2093     note(1,
2094     SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:05\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,
2095     TEXT,\ "VIR_VSL_C16DumpDataToVR4_004: data volume in VR4 2.039 Gibit." \
2096     ),
2097 end;
2098
2099 request(VIR_VSL_C16SAFEmode_001,
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```
2100     START_TIME,VSL_DLTERM_578+03:47:00,  
2101     TITLE, "VIR Safe",  
2102     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
2103     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
2104     KEY, "No_Key")  
2105  
2106     command(1,  
2107         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
2108         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16SAFEmode_001: changing VIR mode into SAFE"\,  
2109         VIR_SAFE()  
2110     ),  
2111     command(2,  
2112         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:01:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
2113         NTEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16SAFEmode_001: dump the error log information"\,  
2114         VIR_TC_ERROR_LOG("DUMP_LOG")  
2115     ),  
2116     note(1,  
2117         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:01:00\,FROM_PREVIOUS_START,  
2118         TEXT,\\"VIR_VSL_C16SAFEmode_001: VIR is in SAFE mode and error log produced"\  
2119     ),  
2120 end;  
2121  
2122 request(VIR_VSL_VMLEND_S8LAMO,  
2123     START_TIME,VSL_DLTERM_578+03:50:00,  
2124     TITLE, "VIR Sequence End - vir_vsl_S8LAMO (ds096)",  
2125     REQUESTOR, "sfonte",  
2126     PROCESSOR, "GSC1",  
2127     KEY, "No_Key")  
2128  
2129     note(1,  
2130         SCHEDULED_TIME,\00:00:00\,FROM_REQUEST_START,  
2131         TEXT,\\"End sequence ds096 - vir_vsl_S8LAMO"\  
2132     ),  
2133 end;  
2134  
2135 $$EOF
```